

GREAT Case Study

Waterwise: Phase 2

Work Package: WP4: Case Study Waterwise

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Case Study Lead: UoB

Author(s): Paul Watson (p.watson@greatermanchester.ac.uk)

Point of Contact: Hendrik Drachsler

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List of Abbreviations

CA	Consortium Agreement
CO	Confidential
DIH	Digital Innovation Hub
DI	Digital Innovation
DMP	Data Management Plan
DoA	Description of Action
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
EC	European Commission
EGE	The European Group on Ethics in Science and New Technologies
GREAT	Games Realising Effective and Affective Transformation
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
UKRI	United Kingdom Research & Innovation
WP	Work Package

1. Executive Summary

Scope: This document reports on phase two GREAT case study cycle with sponsor Waterwise. Phase two proposes a pilot survey through gaming platforms to quantitatively clarify qualitative insights from phase one. At the time of writing the survey has been collaboratively designed and a potential gaming partner identified to deliver the survey. However, due to the positioning of this survey at the end of the GREAT project timeline and priority dynamics of stakeholders, the survey will not be conducted before the close of the GREAT project. This document will therefore report on how the survey builds on work established in phase one, the proposed methodology, provide an account of the collaborative process to date, and reflection on the work completed.

Objective: This phase of the GCS2 case study has two objectives.

Developing insights: Through GCS2 phase one, qualitative discussions facilitated by playful dilemma activities highlighted a clear positive reception to rainwater harvesting to reduce water waste. However, participant knowledge of such practices is also limited. In GCS2 phase two, a pilot survey will be conducted on a gaming community to see if rainwater harvesting is still positively received when cost and maintenance are factored. This has implication to building regulations and policies supporting retrofitting of rainwater harvesting systems.

Assessing method: Surveying a gaming community has shown some success in reach and engagement through case GREAT case studies GCS1, GCS5, GCS8, and GCS9. However, this pilot survey will be delivered through a single gaming partner, similar to GCS1. It is an opportunity to explore what demographics can be reached through a single gaming partner within a rainwater harvesting context and examine with the sponsor how this compares with standard surveying approaches. Within the GREAT project this is an opportunity to explore a mixed methods approach. Examining how a quantitative method of surveying a gaming community builds upon a qualitative climate conversation from GCS2 phase one.

2. Introduction

UK Rainwater Harvesting Survey Approaches

Rainwater harvesting (RWH) is the acquisition and storage of rainwater before it is funnelled into the drainage system (Lee et al., 2016). The size and scale of this technology can range from small house storage to community collection. For example, water butts that collect rainwater for gardening or water tanks that collect rainwater running off a roof for later domestic use.

Rainwater harvesting in the UK has been identified as means to reduce pressure on freshwater supplies (Environment Agency 2025) and help mitigate surface water flooding (The Environmental Audit Committee, 2025). Previous UK research has justified investigating public attitudes towards rainwater harvesting as crucial to identify approaches that increase public uptake and acceptance (Ward, Butler & Memon, 2008; Snelling et al., 2024). Investigations into UK public attitudes towards RWH have focused on three linked areas: Awareness of RWH, perceived barriers and risks, and perceived drivers for uptake. Together, this work builds a picture of a public that is broadly open to the idea of using rainwater, but cautious about cost, disruption, and potential health risks.

When exploring public awareness, the public appear generally receptive to rainwater as an alternative source of water (Booth, et al., 2021; Snelling et al., 2024; Ward, Barr, Memon & Butler, 2013) but are concerned about costs and disruption for installation and maintenance (Database WW., 2020; Ward, Barr, Memon & Butler, 2013). Beyond financial barriers, as RWH use comes closer to body contact, perceptions of risk increases, highlighting that the public may be comfortable to use rainwater for clear non-potable uses, but less for washing and drinking (Ward, Butler & Memon, 2008; Ward, Barr, Memon & Butler, 2013; Egyir, Brown & Arthur, 2016). Prior experience with rainwater harvesting has been explored with studies finding no significant difference in explicit openness to the technology (Ward, Barr, Memon & Butler, 2013), but experience with rainwater harvesting may increase implicit opinions (Snelling et al., 2024). Taken together, UK research shows a public that is open to RWH in principle and most supportive of non-potable uses. Drivers for uptake can be framed to overcome explored barriers, through financial incentives and education on RWH and supporting technologies.

Data collection into UK RWH attitudes has been primarily conducted using questionnaires. Such surveys have been delivered through a variety of methods including post, face to face with public engagement, and through online platforms. Mixed method approaches are present but more limited with follow-up interviews bolstering insights from surveys (Ward, Barr, Memon & Butler, 2013). Survey structure predominantly utilises multiple choice answers and Likert scales. Some innovation is present within these surveys. For example, image to word matching tasks, enabling researchers to explore automatic associations that may not be captured through explicit self-report measures (Snelling et al., 2024). Sample sizes vary considerably across the literature. Both pilot and full studies have reported fewer than 50 respondents, while larger surveys have achieved samples of around 200 participants. Catchment area for a survey is focused to a given location to help identify housing contexts as the backdrop to that data. Overall, the methodological landscape is shaped by structured survey approaches with occasional qualitative additions. The variation in sample size and the localised nature of many surveys highlight the need for caution when generalising findings to the wider UK population.

How Phase Two Builds Upon Phase One

Case study GCS2 (Waterwise) phase one employed the DiBL platform to initiate participatory dialogue around domestic water reduction. Within these facilitated discussions, rainwater harvesting and water recycling emerged as particularly salient themes, with participants expressing strong willingness to adopt such measures if affordable. However, despite this enthusiasm, participants were unable to articulate the underlying technologies or anticipate how such systems might integrate into everyday routines. This knowledge deficit suggests that while rainwater harvesting perceptions are positive, they are not grounded in a clear understanding of the technology or practical implementation.

To extend this inquiry, a second phase of the Waterwise study will deploy a PlanetPlay pilot survey to a gaming community to quantitatively examine public perceptions when weighing the key benefits and drawbacks of rainwater harvesting systems. The survey aims to bridge the gap between positive attitudes and practical understanding to enable assessment if rainwater harvesting remains a desirable domestic technology. If previous literature is generalisable to a gaming community, we would expect to see a positive reception to RWH but key barriers of finance and maintenance issues. Obtaining a more comprehensive understanding of public attitudes to rainwater harvesting may inform UK housebuilding regulations and the focus of supportive water sustainability initiatives.

This work can also be seen in conjunction with phase one of GCS2 in three important ways.

- Firstly, it extends insights developed in small group discussions from phase one and brings the GCS2 case study into a mixed methods approach where qualitative insights are also explored through quantitative lens. Through this method the generalisability of insights developed within GCS2 phase one can be evaluated and explored through quantitative data (Creswell & Clark, 2017). From the perspective of the GREAT project this represents the use of both principal methodologies in a mixed methods context. The playful small group discussions, and distribution of surveys within gaming communities. Due to the multiple stakeholders within one GREAT project case study, having both quantitative and qualitative data provides points of reflection for all parties to consider the direction of the broader GREAT project (Tobi & Kampen, 2018).
- Secondly this quantitative data can underpin activities and discussions in future qualitative iterations. For example, use key findings from a surveyed gaming community to underpin the content for playful dilemma games. This cyclical use of insights between qualitative and quantitative data may create a form of dialogue between public groups.
- The combination of qualitative playful discussions from phase one and surveying a gaming community about perceptions of RWH represents a meaningful extension of previous survey practice. Potentially offering access to demographics that have been

largely absent from previous UK studies. Additionally, with the right cadence, may offer a means to repeat surveys to explore changes in views across time.

Research Questions

Three GREAT project research questions shape the line of enquiry for this phase of work.

RQ 1.1 Which games-based activities can be used to elicit, represent and communicate citizens' views on social dilemmas?

- **Attitudes and Preferences:** Do individuals from gaming communities see value in rainwater harvesting systems when confronted with the practical costs and maintenance of such systems.

RQ 1.2 How effective are games-based activities in eliciting, representing and communicating citizens' views on social dilemmas?

- **Triangulation of between approaches:** The survey builds upon the insights gathered from the playful, small group discussions used within the GREAT project. Utilising the depth of discussion to draw out important insights that require broader examination across demographics. This combined approach enables triangulation of qualitative and quantitative data that may strengthen insights for case study sponsors.
- **A new methodology within the GREAT project:** The use of both discussion and survey approaches within the same case study represents exploration of both as a single methodology. How attitudes and preferences developed through such discussion can inform quantitative surveys distributed within gaming communities.

RQ 1.3 How efficient is the use of games-based activities in eliciting, representing and communicating citizens' views on social dilemmas?

- **Further exploration of the Planet Play survey approach:** The Planet Play survey will be conducted through a single gaming community. This distribution strategy has been central to previous studies, including GCS1, GCS5, GCS8, and GCS9. However, unlike GCS5, GCS8, and GCS9 which engaged multiple gaming partners, this survey is expected to rely on only one gaming partner organisation. This constraint provides an opportunity to further examine the extent to which reach and engagement can be achieved when collaboration is limited to a single gaming partner like GCS1.

3. Methodology

The survey has been designed but not conducted. This section will outline the intent of the methodology to be, an account of the survey development, as well as barriers to survey administration.

Research Design

This pilot survey is part of a descriptive, non-experimental research design. The aim of the survey is to describe attitudes and preferences to rainwater harvesting systems within the homes of a gaming community. The survey examines whether members of the gaming community perceive value in such systems when presented with both benefits and practical considerations regarding cost and maintenance.

Survey Development

Initial contact with Waterwise about phase two of the GCS2 case study was made 16/07/2025. This was to discuss findings from phase one and consider direction for phase two. Due to scheduling conflicts, this discussion could not be held until 28/08/2025. The results of this meeting yielded three viable research directions for the survey:

- 1) Hose water bans
- 2) Water recycling/re-use in the homes
- 3) Educating citizens on water use

Following discussions with academic collaborators and PlanetPlay, rainwater harvesting was selected as the focal water recycling method for the survey. This decision was grounded in findings from phase one, where participants frequently expressed positive attitudes toward such systems but demonstrated limited understanding of their practical implementation. Based on these findings it was determined to assess whether public support remains strong when potential benefits are considered alongside expectations around cost, maintenance, and integration into daily life.

When engaging multiple groups to collaborate there can be tensions with epistemic backgrounds and work priorities that inhibit collaboration (Tobi & Kampen, 2018). In the survey development, Waterwise input was initially postponed due to holiday and workload dynamics. Due to this delay, the survey was internally developed between academic partners and PlanetPlay in a shared Google Document and refined through iterative cycles of comments. These GREAT academic partners regularly met and were used to using the Google platform for

project. Google Docs represented a well-used form of communication between GREAT project members, which is crucial for interdisciplinary work (Tobi & Kampen, 2018). Being a shared online space, partners could access and contribute to the document at their convenience. Iterative development was used as the specificity of the task and overlapping knowledge backgrounds of the partners facilitated a convergence (Wynn & Eckert, 2017) of progressive iteration. Once a satisfactory draft was reached, it was submitted to Waterwise for review and further iteration on 15/10/2025. The review process was completed by 31/10/2025.

The aims of the survey are to explore:

- What benefits of rainwater harvesting most resonate with the public.
- What drawbacks (maintenance, space) are key concerns for the public.
- Does the survey itself better inform the public of rainwater harvesting technologies.
- What cost would the public be willing to bear for a rainwater harvesting system.
- Demographic information of nationality, gender, perceived financial stability, and accommodation type.

Establishing a Gaming Partner for Survey Distribution

The gaming partner selection will be led by the industry partner, PlanetPlay. This selection is convenient but represents a potential 300 respondents across nationalities. From previous experience, this could lead to 20-50 UK respondents. This number will gather enough respondents similar to other UK pilots (Ward, Butler & Memon, 2008) and compare to other nationalities.

The gaming partner was brought into the GREAT project very late in the cycle (27/11/25). Before agreeing to host the survey, they needed time for their own legal advisor to review the proposed questions and content. They were willing to run the survey but felt that, because of competing events and surveys over the festive period, it would be more effective to launch in the new year. The intended date was pushed back to February 2026 to avoid “survey fatigue”. This shift placed the survey outside the original GREAT project timeline.

3.2 Participant selection

Participants will be those who take part through the gaming community. No participant selection criteria will be applied. To gather data on the demographic of those that take part in the survey, both demographic questions will be asked in the survey and browser information will be assessed. The demographic information was discussed in consultation with Waterwise and academic colleagues. Within the survey, participants will be asked to give their age, gender, nationality, home type, and perceived financial situation. Through the web browser used to host

the survey we will gather language used and city/country location based on their IP address. These data will enable verification of survey reach and demographic breadth.

3.3 Ethical Considerations

Ethical approval for this study has been granted from the University of Greater Manchester Ethics Process (approval number: AUTOTEHP00799). The survey will be optional for the gaming community that partners with this study. No deception is required in this work. Before participants take part in the survey, they are informed that they are taking part in a survey about rainwater harvesting. They are informed that no personally identifiable data will be gathered and that anonymised data will be used for academic research. Participants will have the option to not continue the survey at any point. Data gathered from this survey would be stored securely in password protected online storage.

3.4 Mapping of RQ's to Case Study:

Table 1. Mapping of research questions to the case study

Revised research objectives and questions	<i>Simple formulation in terms of GREAT</i>	<i>Yes/No</i>
RQ1. To understand how games-based activities can be designed to provide a link between citizens and policy makers.		
RQ1.1 Which games-based activities can be used to elicit, represent and communicate citizens' views on social dilemmas?	<i>How can GREAT be achieved?</i>	YES
RQ1.2 How effective are games-based activities in eliciting, representing and communicating citizens' views on social dilemmas?	<i>Does GREAT do what we want it to do?</i>	YES
RQ1.3 How efficient is the use of games-based activities in eliciting, representing and communicating citizens' views on social dilemmas?	<i>How much work is it to use the GREAT approach?</i>	YES

RQ1.4 How widely applicable are games-based activities in eliciting, representing and communicating citizens' views on social dilemmas, and which variables need to be taken into consideration when adapting them to different contexts?	<i>How widely applicable is what we do?</i>	NO
RQ2. To understand the benefits and risks to citizens, policy stakeholders and policy makers, of using games-based activities as a link between citizens and policy makers.		
RQ2.1 What are the affordances of games in eliciting and representing citizens' views in relation to social dilemmas.	<i>What is it about GREAT that makes it good for gathering and representing opinions and attitudes?</i>	NO
RQ2.2 What are the benefits and risks to policy makers and policy stakeholders of using games-based activities to elicit, represent and communicate citizens' views on social dilemmas?	<i>What is good and bad about GREAT for policy stakeholders and policy makers?</i>	NO
RQ2.3 What are the benefits and risks to citizens of using games-based activities to elicit, represent and communicate their views on social dilemmas?	<i>What is good and bad about GREAT for citizens?</i>	NO

3.4.1 Detail the design process for the case study:

Table 2. Detailing the design process for the case study

Step of Case Study Cycle	Overview of the Eight-Step Cycle <i>Provide a brief description of each step in the case study process.</i>
Create and Prioritise Research Topics (Step 1) <i>Document the outcomes of initial workshops.</i>	Email communication and a video conferencing discussion was used to evaluate the qualitative discussion findings used in phase 1 of the GCS2 case study and explore how the addition of quantitative survey data would validate and add detail to these findings.

	<p>This survey also builds directly on insights gathered through the DiBL qualitative approach, and is an opportunity to use both approaches within one GREAT case study.</p> <p>A list of potential survey directions was outlined:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 4) Hose water bans 5) Water recycling/re-use in the homes 6) Educating citizens on water use
<p>Collaborate in Study Design (Step 2)</p> <p><i>Describe the collaborative case study design process.</i></p>	<p>After discussions with academic project partners and technical implementers from PlanetPlay, it was decided to focus the survey on water re-use approaches. This has implications for building regulations that are currently under discussion within the UK.</p> <p>Additionally, this would expand insights that emerged from phase one of this case study and enable exploration of combining both the qualitative and quantitative methods used in the GREAT project.</p> <p>A key academic design decision explored at this step was whether or not to gamify the survey in some form. After exploring the literature, it was decided not to pursue the playful/gamified structures for the survey. This is due to mixed literature results on engagement through such mechanisms and diminishing time to implement such an approach technically and form a design perspective.</p>
<p>Collaborate in Design of Games-Based Activities (Step 3)</p> <p><i>Explain the collaborative design of game activities.</i></p>	<p>Initially, it was anticipated that Waterwise and its partners would lead the development of the survey content, given their expertise and alignment with ongoing UK water security consultations. However, due to scheduling constraints across Waterwise and associated organisations, communication delays emerged. To address these delays, the research team developed a preliminary survey draft, drawing on insights gathered during earlier phases of collaboration (steps 1 and 2). This drafting process involved representatives from the University of Bolton (case study lead), ZSI (evaluation), PlanetPlay (technical infrastructure), and UNIR (WP2 leaders).</p>

	Survey was shown to Waterwise for review and discussion which resulted in final survey design.
Piloting and Gathering Data (Step 4) <i>Document the piloting phase and data collection.</i>	Games partner for survey distribution has been identified. However, due to gaming partner priorities, the survey will not be conducted within the GREAT project timeline. Therefore step 4 and beyond are not engaged with at the time of writing.

4. Reflections

The development and distribution of the survey has underscored the challenges of coordinating input and resources across multiple large organisations, particularly when the task is perceived as additional to routine responsibilities.

4.1 Partnership Dynamics

Waterwise showed clear commitment to the survey, but competing priorities, holiday periods, and wider organisational pressures slowed progress. This exposed a mismatch between the project timeline and the sponsor’s internal calendar. Although the survey was ultimately completed with input from academic, industry, and domain experts, these delays pushed distribution into a later window. Developing the survey internally and then seeking targeted review from the sponsor proved to be an effective way to reduce their workload and accelerate collaboration. In hindsight, adopting this approach earlier, once delays became visible, could have streamlined development and review even further.

The use of gaming partners offers access to broad and often hard to reach demographics, but it also depends on protecting player engagement and the partner’s reputation. Surveys must therefore be timed around the partner’s own community rhythms, as they are best placed to judge when their players have the capacity or appetite for additional content. Ignoring this risks damaging trust within the community and placing the partner in a difficult position. Our collaboration highlighted the challenges of bringing a key partner on board late, when their schedule was already full and there was little room to integrate an external survey. Earlier conversations and clearer alignment of calendars might have reduced this pressure. It also became clear that academic teams need a better understanding of the operational constraints that gaming partners work within. More open discussion of these constraints could help set realistic expectations and support the development of alternative plans when timelines shift.

4.2 Methodological insights

Timing is a methodological constraint when working with gaming partners. Games run frequent events, release new content, and manage ongoing engagement. Surveys that do not support these priorities are unlikely to be promoted and may even be seen as disruptive to community flow or brand identity. Even well aligned surveys depend on finding a quiet moment in the community calendar. Launching a survey between major events or seasonal campaigns increases the chance of support from both the gaming partner and the players. A themed period such as a climate month can also create a natural space for the survey to be shared without competing with core activities.

4.3 Future Research

Based on the case study work achieved, there are some interesting lines of inquiry that could be followed.

- The survey is now fully designed and technically ready for distribution, yet the process has highlighted several areas that require deeper understanding before this approach can be used effectively with gaming communities. Working with a gaming partner raised important questions about how such surveys are perceived internally and how they fit within the rhythms of community management. It became clear that distribution is not simply a logistical step but a relational and strategic one that depends on trust, timing, and alignment with the partner's priorities.
- The experience also highlighted gaps in our understanding of how players themselves interpret research invitations within a gaming environment. Without this insight, it is difficult to judge whether such surveys feel relevant, intrusive, or welcome. Exploring player perceptions would be essential for designing future studies that are both respectful and effective
- The survey was developed in response to insights generated through the playful dilemmas used in phase one of GCS2. This raised important questions about how these two approaches might speak to one another. An opportunity to reflect on whether a quantitative survey through a gaming community can meaningfully validate, challenge, or extend themes that emerged from qualitative playful approaches.
- The case study also highlights the potential for a more deliberate dialogue between the two methods. Survey findings could help identify dilemma themes and where new dilemmas might be needed to probe emerging questions. Equally, the dilemmas themselves may shape future survey items. Future work could explore a more cyclical connection between the quantitative and qualitative approaches. Each informing the next iteration of the other.

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